
**ANALYSIS OF PRICE DYNAMICS OF THE AGRICULTURAL MARKETS IN
MAHARASHTRA**

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Abstract: Price dynamics in the agricultural markets are investigated to market integration, market efficiency, the relationships between arrivals and prices, inter-market comparisons of prices. Based on analysis several policy implications are in terms of interventions. the dynamics of prices analyzing the functioning of the markets. This study considered spot prices prevailing in different markets in Maharashtra for selected commodities that were compiled on a day-to-day basis in terms of “Total arrivals”, “Maximum Price”, “Minimum Price” and “Average (Modal) Price” for each commodity.

This paper on the analysis of price dynamics in the agricultural markets in Maharashtra examining the price dynamic of markets and their preliminary analysis – where all transactions, including auctions, are regulated by the statutory market committees. including profiling of data, seasonality in arrivals, charting of data series, etc. and summarize decades of research on spatial and price dynamics, and conclude on a potential direction for future research.

Keywords: Price dynamics; policy implications; spot prices; commodity; auctions; profiling of data; preliminary; analysis;

Introduction:

One of the main issues against agricultural trade is to identify price dynamics of the market, also called integration analysis, to identify whether the markets are integrated or not. For that study the most important marketing centers for agricultural commodities are Agricultural Produce Market Committees (APMC), where all transactions are regulated. The data on prices and quantities for each transaction recorded by the and they are then compiled on a day-to-day basis in terms of Total arrivals, Maximum, Minimum and Average (Modal) Price for each commodity. The daily average (modal) price is defined as the largest number of transactions during the day.

For this study researcher has selected i.e. Tur (Arhar) is one of the major crops in pulses. In terms of production in India Maharashtra stands first. Tur is a Kharif crop and its main marketing season is during December – February. This commodity is also traded in the futures market, these markets are called “Commodity Exchanges” and the prices are called ‘Futures’ Prices.

For each transaction are manually recorded by the officers in each APMC in terms of arrival and spot prices, these daily transaction summaries then transmitted to Government, Farmers and stakeholders. The prices prevailing in the APMCs are spot prices. To understand the price dynamics of selected commodity researchers has selected top ten APMC’s in terms of highest arrivals of Tur commodity.

Objectives of study:

The compilation and analysis of the daily data pertaining to around 10 markets was attempted with following objectives:

- Consolidating daily data in to the data on weekly, monthly and yearly basis and preparing a time-series for each commodity and market
- Representativeness of the selected Markets
- Examining the relationships between arrivals and prices
- Making inter-market comparisons (integration) of prices
- To find out trends and seasonality in prices.

Literature Review:

The price formation process is simple from one point of view but terribly complex from another. The opportunity costs of production, consumer value, negotiating power, and social and psychological considerations are the four major factors determining price (F. Norwood, L. Lusk,2008). Agricultural price movements are caused by different forces according to the length of time involved. Long time movements, for example, are caused by changes in production, in the technology of production, etc. These forces are slow to move. Short-time movements are caused by different forces, annual variations in the weather, wars, boom and depressions (G.S. Shepherd,1947). Agriculture in India, especially during the monsoon season, is highly vulnerable to the extreme variability in climatic factors and this affects production, demand and prices of agricultural commodities (Kumar et al. 2014). The shortcoming of spatial price correlations to evaluate market integration involves the influences of common components such

as population growth, inflation or climate patterns. As documented by (Abdulai, 2006). Goodwin and Schroeder (1991) called “perfectly integrated” the markets that show a one-for-one relationship across price changes; Monke and Petzel (1984, p. 482) defined as “integrated” the markets in which prices of differentiated products do not behave independently. To analyzing prices to examine their temporal behavior is to undertake the usual time series analysis of price data for a period of time. This helps to isolate the trend, seasonal fluctuations, cyclical fluctuations and the irregular fluctuations in commodity prices (IGNOU,2017).

Methodology:

- **Representativeness of the selected Markets**

Rank	District	Market
1	Latur	Latur
2	Wardha	Hinganghat
3	Amarawati	Amarawati
4	Buldhana	Khamgaon
5	Jalna	Jalna
6	Washim	Karanja
7	Amarawati	Achalpur
8	Buldhana	Malkapur
9	Osmanabad	Murum
10	Solapur	Barshi

Agricultural commodities are mostly traded in APMCs in Maharashtra and Tur (Arhar) is also traded in many APMC’s for this study based on data of arrival from October 2010 to September 2022, top 10 APMC has selected for study to analyze the price dynamics in these market with various methodologies like trend, seasonality, market integration and data accuracy.

The table-1 gives the Top 10 Markets of Maharashtra. The production was relatively highest in recent years

Table-1 Top 10 Markets of Maharashtra for Tur

Prices of Tur in the Selected Markets:

The monthly prices of Tur are shown in the following chart. In order not to clutter the chart, only a few markets are shown. The Tur prices show a continuous rising trend. The prices seem to move parallel with each other. The statistical analysis of these monthly prices shows the following:

- There is no relationship between local arrivals.
- All the markets show a very high and positive correlation among themselves. The correlation coefficients for monthly prices among different markets are always higher than 0.90
- All the markets show a very high and positive correlation with the wholesale price index (WPI) for Tur. The index is calculated on an all-India basis. The correlation coefficient between each market and WPI is always higher than 0.63.
- The Tur market appears to be very integrated, with least influence of local factors like arrivals.

The above conclusions are that the prices of Tur in all markets are strongly integrated with each other; on the other hand, arrival in all markets have not shown any correlation between them,

they need to be reinforced with further study.

Figure 1. Monthly Prices of Tur (Amravati, Hinganghat and Latur Market)

Relationships between arrivals and prices:

The market price and arrival behavior of Tur during October 2004 to September 2022 was examined. Supply and demand behavior of Tur shows 0 correlation means the highest arrival comes in the market in the months of January, February and March and prices decrease in these months, when the prices increase in August and September at that point there is no arrival in the

market.

Figure 2. Monthly Prices and Arrivals index of Tur

● **Trend in Prices**

The market price behavior of Tur during October 2004 to September 2022 in the Latur Agriculture Produce Market Committee was examined using descriptive statistics. The analysis of Tur prices showed that on an average, the mean prices of Tur varied between Rs 4618 per quintal in the selected market, whereas, minimum and maximum price per quintal varied between Rs 1475 to Rs 15000. Prices of Tur show a slightly rising trend

Equation of Trend: $y = 21.18x + 2177 \quad R^2 = 0.4719$

Figure 3. Monthly Prices of Tur in Latur APMC

Where x is defining trend in price. The variable Trend (expressed as 1, 2, 3, etc.) as Proxy for both rise in price level as also rising net demand. In above equation R^2 explains 47% variation and shows an increasing trend.

Seasonality: Seasonal variation is measured in seasonal index. An index value for each period of the time series in a year. This implies that if monthly data are considered seasonal indices, one

for each month. The following methods use seasonal indices to measure seasonal variations of a time-series data. The index is based on a mean of 100, with the degree of seasonality measured by variations away from the base. The index is based on a mean of 100 of 12 months in a year

Figure 4. Seasonal Price Index of Tur

Its means Prices of Tur 6%, 4% respectively in August and September are higher than mean price and 5% price decrease in October and May (Figure 4).

Conclusion:

The price dynamics in agricultural commodities has examined with the selected agro commodity for study i.e. Tur(Arhar). To examined price with the help of representative market, because Tur are traded in many market and many district, for this study researcher top 10 market selected on the basis of highest arrival, these markets covers 8 districts and from these market Latur APMC placed on first rank so for this study Latur market considered to representative market of Tur. a On the basis of the price dynamics examined Overall, the study results show as follows. (1) Tur Prices and Arrival has no correlation between them when price increases arrival has decreased (2) but prevailed prices in all top 10 APMC has strongly correlated coefficients greater than 0.90 it means the markets are well integrated. (3) After the examined of Tur prices results shows the

prices are shows increasing trend up to 47 %, as compared to the other influencing factor on prices, another factor is most important in price determination is seasonality, in this study seasonality are examined and result indicated that there is a Tur price are seasonally affected, Prices are high in the months of August and September and Low in October and May.

Overall, the price dynamics study shows that Tur prices are slightly influenced by trend and seasonality but The above conclusions are tentative; they need to be reinforced with further study. However, they suggest that the detailed econometric and time series analysis could be limited with fewer, robust markets, which are representative, and have sufficient continuous and reliable data.

References:

- i. Abdulai, A. (2006) "Spatial Integration and Price Transmission in Agricultural Commodity Markets in Sub-Saharan Africa" in Sarris, A. and Hallam, D. (Eds.) *Agricultural Commodity Markets and Trade: New Approaches to Analysing Market Structure and Instability*. FAO. Edward Elgar
- ii. Barry K. Goodwin & Ted C. Schroeder (1991) "**Price Dynamics in International Wheat Markets**," *Canadian Journal of Agricultural Economics/Revue canadienne d'agroeconomie*, Canadian Agricultural Economics Society/Societe canadienne d'agroeconomie, vol. 39(2), pages 237-254, July.
- iii. F. Bailey Norwood, Jayson L. Lusk (2008) - *Agricultural marketing and price analysis*, Pearson/Prentice Hall, Technology & Engineering
- iv. Geoffrey S. Shepherd, (1947) - *Agricultural Price Analysis*, Second Edition, Revised, The Iowa State College Press, Amfs,Lowa
- v. IGNOU (2017), Block-4 Agricultural Marketing and Price Analysis, <https://egyankosh.ac.in/bitstream/123456789/27388/1/Block-4.pdf>
- vi. Kumar, Praduman & Joshi, P.K., (2014). "Input Subsidy vs Farm Technology — Which is More Important for Agricultural Development?," *Agricultural Economics Research Review*, Agricultural Economics Research Association (India), vol. 27(1).
- vii. Monke, E., Todd P. (1984) *Market Integration: An Application to International Trade in Cotton*. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*. 66:481-87.